

HIDDEN PAIN IN ORPHANS: A THEORETICAL NOTE

Ms. Anmol Shekhar Srivastava* Research scholar (Psychology), C.S.J.M. University, Kanpur
Dr. Jaya Bharti** Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, A.N.D.N.N.M.M. (C.S.J.M. University), Kanpur

Abstract

It is well established that being an orphan negatively affects a child's formative years. Losing one or both parents is one of the most horrifying tragedies that make children feel helpless, lonely, and insecure. The majority of orphans encounter sizable compounded hazards that frequently result in unfavourable consequences because of their vulnerability and propensity to physical and psychological dangers. They have emotions like abandonment, loneliness, and future anxiety. The financial, developmental, and emotional support that children and adolescents receive from their caregivers is crucial for their growth, and the loss of a parent or other caregiver can have a long-term negative impact on a child's achievement. Anxiety, sadness, PTSD, substance misuse, suicide, poor academic performance, higher percentages of high school dropouts, economic hardship, and general instability can all be the effects of losing one or both parents. This paper will give the conceptual clarification of the term “orphan”, the psychological perspective of orphans, and the psychological effect of bereavement. It discusses the pain, suffering, and struggles faced by them.

Keywords: orphan, pain, children, India, bereavement

Introduction

Orphan children are considered vulnerable because of their traumatic pasts and the realities of life. Any child under the age of 18 who has lost one or both of their parents to death is considered an orphan, according to UNICEF. Around the world, there were reportedly 140 million orphans in 2015, estimated to be 153 million as of right now. The majority of orphans live in developing nations. In 2015, there were 7.3 million orphans in Eastern Europe and Central Asia, 61 million in Asia, 52 million in Africa, and 10 million in Latin America. The majority of orphaned children worldwide reside in Asia and Africa. These children are frequently abandoned, becoming victims of malnutrition, sexual assault, illness, and even death. Aside from physical pain and suffering, they also experience psychological pain and suffering throughout their lives.

Statement of the Problem

The formative years of a child are known to be negatively impacted when he/she turns into an orphan. Losing one or both parents is one of the most traumatic traumas that leave children feeling helpless, alone, and insecure. There are many hidden pains, sufferings, and struggles that these children go through.

Objectives of the study

- To understand and describe the hidden pains of orphan children.
- To understand the psychological perspective of being an orphan.
- To describe the psychological effects of bereavement on orphan children.

Review Literature

Various studies show that orphans face numerous problems throughout their lives. In a study by Sengendo & Nambi (1997), it was found that due to orphan children's vulnerability and predisposition to physical and psychological dangers, most orphans face significant accumulated risks that frequently have unfavourable outcomes. According to another study by Sebsibe, Fekadu & Molalign (2014), Children who live in orphanages are more likely to experience adverse life events like abuse and neglect and to struggle with psychosocial problems. Kaur et al (2018), discovered that orphans had more severe behavioural, emotional, and distress issues than other non-orphaned children. According

to the study by Mohammadzadeh et al (2017), adolescents living in orphanages have been found to have significant rates of depression, stress, and anxiety as well as low self-esteem.

Since most children without parental care are susceptible and inclined to physical and psychological difficulties, the loss of their parents can have tremendous cumulative impacts that are frequently unfavourable.

Research Methodology

Many different computerized databases were searched such as Research Gate, Google Scholar, PsycINFO, EBSCO, Crossref, PubMed, Scopus database, and published research papers like Dissertation and abstracts. The keywords used to look through the databases were significant to behavioural, psychological, and emotional problems related to orphan children.

Results and Discussion

Orphans in India

The number of orphans in India is shocking. Nearly 2 crore orphans live in India, which has a larger population than all of Sri Lanka. SOS Children's Villages' extensive research is the source of this information. According to estimates from UNICEF and other studies, there were almost 12 million orphans and abandoned children in India in 2007 and the government's Childline service.

According to a press release published on March 2, 2022, by PIB Delhi, the Ministry of Women and Child Development found it very shocking and at odds with field data when estimates of the number of children affected by Covid-19-related orphanhood were published in the Lancet on February 24, 2022. According to a Lancet investigation, covid in India has resulted in the deaths of more than 19 lakh children's primary caregivers. However, field research indicates that these conclusions are inconsistent with the reality in India. According to field data gathered from the States/UTs and compiled, the numbers for India are close to 1.53 lakhs, where the death of a parent might have been caused by COVID, a natural, unnatural cause, or any other reason during the pandemic. Since April 1, 2020, all children who have lost their parents (either one or both) for any reason have been tracked by the National Commission for the Protection of Child Rights (NCPCR). To provide appropriate care, protection, and benefits to all such children, the data/information of each child is collected, confirmed, and analyzed.

India has the most orphaned children in the world, with a total population of 22 million, according to a survey by an organization called Orphan Outreach. In India, one in ten children will grow up to orphan. This figure may be much higher than we think.

Conceptual clarification of Orphan

Defining what the term "orphan" means can be challenging because it varies from society to society and offers a challenge to the idea of an "orphan." Definitions can range from very broad and general to very particular and encompassing, with a huge range in between. Even in this more limited sense, there are still ambiguities over what separates an orphan from a non-orphan because the definition of an orphan has changed over time and is widely accepted in contemporary society. The term "orphan" was used to describe both children whose parents had passed away and children whose parents were unable or unwilling to support them, throughout the early modern era of Western history (approximately the 15th to the 18th centuries). Children may be left orphaned due to their parents' economic difficulty, prolonged military or naval service, chronic disease, or widowhood. A child's circumstances may be different under more modern definitions of orphans, yet they may still be just as complex as those under older reports.

A minor is considered to have experienced bereavement because of "the death or disappearance of, the abandonment or desertion of, or the separation from or loss of both parents," according to a legal definition used in the United States. An orphan is a child under the age of 18 who has lost both of their parents (George, 2011). A person who has no surviving parents to take care of them is referred to as an orphan in common parlance. Any child who has lost one parent is classified as an orphan by organizations like UNICEF, UNAIDS, and others. In this approach, a child who has lost their mother

is considered a "maternal orphan," a child who has lost their father is considered a "paternal orphan," and a child, teen, or baby who has lost both parents is considered a "double orphan." In contrast, the term "half-orphan" was once used to refer to children who had only lost one parent. And a "social orphan" is a child who has been abandoned or whose parents have given up on him due to hardships like poverty, drunkenness, or incarceration (Dillon, 2008).

What does it mean to be an orphan?

Children depend on their parents to be there for them throughout their childhood and even after. If the child loses any of his/her parents, i.e., a father or a mother, it is going to be a tough life forever. However, it is more than just losing a person; it is a loss of care, support, attention, hope, etc. The child will be called an orphan until his/her death. Being an orphan means being deprived of the necessities of life.

Orphans stand apart from the rest of society in a blatant way. They are the enduring opposite. Orphans are a visible representation of the anxiety over abandonment that all people feel. Orphans are excluded and segregated because they lack ties to the familial network that contributes to a person's identity. They did nothing to earn this status as an outcast; rather, it was brought about by their deviation from the socially accepted "normal" pattern.

First and foremost, children are very concerned about death as a permanent condition. Children whose cognitive development has not yet reached an acceptable level see an absence as a voyage and are unable to comprehend that a parent would not return. The subsequent step is finality, in which all aspects of life end simultaneously with death. All things come to life for children. They are more likely to comprehend that everything that has a life also has an end as they get older. Children begin to worry that this will happen to all of their loved ones at this stage (Schonfeld, 1993).

The Psychological Perspective of an Orphan

A child who is an orphan has a psychology that is somewhat different from a child who is not an orphan. Due to the lack of parental guidance in completing his tasks successfully, the orphan youngster thinks and acts independently. He makes poor decisions on numerous occasions, sometimes leading him to the edge of a cliff. On the other hand, a child who is not an orphan is always supported by his parents, who make decisions for him and help him think through his options. What matters most is that they stand by him when he needs them. The child living in an orphanage belongs to the orphanage society rather than the society in which he or she lives. If they're lucky enough to be taken care of by an orphanage, children in orphanages only have one place to call home. However, if they aren't, there will be an issue since they'll end up homeless, begging, or working at an early age. It is quite risky for the child to be an orphan and homeless at a young age because he will be susceptible to sexual harassment from adults, or he may turn out to be a criminal in his very young years due to the circumstances and situation.

Due to their vulnerability and predisposition to physical and psychological dangers, most orphans face significant accumulated risks that frequently have unfavourable outcomes. In a study of the psychological effects of orphanhood, the children could tell the difference in their parents' quality of life, when their parents were healthy, when they got sick, and when they passed away. When it became apparent that their parents were ill, the majority of kids lost hope, along with their sadness and sense of helplessness. Many of them experienced depression and anger after being adopted. Children who lived alone or with widowed fathers were much more depressed. Additionally, compared to children who lived with their mothers who were widowed, these children were more outwardly focused. (Sengendo & Nambi, 1997)

Due to their limited capacity to handle intense emotions for long periods, young children often fluctuate between confronting and avoiding their feelings to prevent becoming overwhelmed. Losses are so distressing and terrifying. These feelings could not be recognised as being related to grief since they might manifest as irrational conduct or furious outbursts rather than as sadness. Furthermore, young children generally transition from grieving reactions to a rapid search for and accepting of substitute people because their wants to be cared for and connected to are strong and immediate.

Children are likely to exhibit grief-related affects and behaviour on an intermittent basis for many years after a loss occurs, unlike adults who can handle a year or more of intense mourning. Different strong reactions to the loss typically will be revived, reviewed, and processed repeatedly at successive stages of continued development. Therefore, it's crucial to understand the unique characteristics of children's grief and not assume that their outward behaviours or the way they express their feelings will necessarily reflect their inner turmoil when working with children who have experienced a loss.

The Pain, Suffering, and Struggles

A child who is raised in an orphanage will always have eternal nightmares about it. The reason he ended up an orphan without a constant parent to lean on is a mystery to orphans. Without assistance from reliable sources (the parents), he is weak and disoriented in this vast, dark world. His desire is completely destroyed by the issues and misfortunes that keep knocking him down at every stage of his life.

A child's early years are known to be negatively impacted by being an orphan. One of the most traumatic traumas that leave children feeling helpless, alone, and insecure is losing one or both parents. Tragedy has a stronger influence on a child when he is younger, especially when his mother is lost because she is the one who cares for him and stays with him throughout his life's development. Many children are forced or driven into dangerous jobs to make a living, putting their lives in grave danger. Early in childhood, being an orphan can be painful. Many people who have both parents present do not realize the privilege they have. Orphans frequently lack meaningful experience when discussing parenting, family, and kids. Children who live in orphanages are more likely to experience adverse life events like abuse and neglect and to struggle with psychosocial problems (Sebsibe, Fekadu & Molalign, 2014). It was discovered that orphans had more severe behavioural, emotional, and distress issues than other non-orphaned children (Kaur et al, 2018). Adolescents living in orphanages have been found to have significant rates of depression, stress, and anxiety as well as low self-esteem (Mohammadzadeh et al, 2017). Even as an adult, the feeling of becoming an orphan after a parent passes away can be debilitating. They have emotions like abandonment, loneliness, and future anxiety. A mother or a father, who offers a place of safety for their child on a psychological level or in any other way that helped him feel at rest in the world, is no longer alive.

The financial, developmental, and emotional support that children and adolescents receive from their caregivers is crucial for their growth, and the loss of a parent or other caregiver can have a long-term negative impact on a child's achievement. Anxiety, sadness, PTSD, substance misuse, suicide, poor academic performance, higher percentages of high school dropouts, economic hardship, and general instability can all be the effects of losing one or both parents.

According to the literature, after their parents pass away, orphans face mental and psychological pain, which results in their poverty, exploitation in the homes of their relatives, and the loss of educational chances. The growing body of research indicates that older orphans are more likely to experience lower psychosocial outcomes because orphans' poor mental health outcomes persist and deteriorate into later adolescence. Additionally, older orphans are more likely to drop out of school, which is made worse by the absence of family support. There are numerous established causes for the high likelihood of school dropout. For instance, being a maternal orphan makes a child nutritionally sensitive and more likely to drop out of school, and orphans who live in houses with children or young people in charge are more likely to experience detrimental effects on their educational needs. Particularly older siblings stop attending school to find work to care for the younger siblings.

Emotional pain develops once a parent dies. The orphans are prone to long-term psychological issues like despair, rage, anxiety, and melancholy feelings and have the propensity to withdraw and isolate themselves. They have psychological issues as a result of not processing their experience of loss.

People who live in homes where children or young people are in charge endure buried grief that appears as a protracted bereavement. Another significant obstacle and cause of stress for orphans

managing households are learning how to take care of their siblings without any prior preparation or family help.

Some of the hidden pains in orphans can be mentioned as follows:

- **Isolation:** Isolation is one of the worst things that most orphan children experience. Children who have parents can express their thoughts and feelings to them. For an orphan, the sentiment and viewpoint could be forgotten during their lives. Even if an orphan has something to say, their parental history may prevent them from speaking for the rest of the time. This may result in complete seclusion from society at large.
- **Lack of Parental Guidance:** Parental advice is much missed by orphans. Parental guidance is beneficial, influential, and effective in the lives of children. Without parental supervision, children in public frequently become the black sheep in their families. The fact is that these children don't get the fundamental guidance that comes from their parents. Additionally, it means that young children will base their selections on their level of comprehension. But it's still a serious threat that continues to exist in an orphan's life.
- **Poor Well-being:** Well-being is the state of being at ease, healthy, or content. Even after a child has passed the age of 18 at which they become an orphan, maternal death has a negative effect on their psychosocial wellness. They are less able to establish coping mechanisms as a result of missing their mothers, which caused them to become isolated, depressed, hopeless, unsatisfied, and fearful of the future. (Ntuli, Mokgatle, & Madiba, 2020)
- **Emotional issues:** Orphans go through sadness, general anxiety, tension, violence, low self-esteem, and externalizing and internalizing behaviours. (Priyadarshini and Rathnasabapathy, 2020)
- **Suffer Child labour:** The exploitation of children under the age of 18 through any type of employment that stops them from having a typical childhood and has a negative influence on them on all fronts—physically, cognitively, emotionally, morally, spiritually, and socially—is known as child labour. Many orphans are compelled to work arduous jobs that seriously endanger their lives to make a living.
- **Identity loss:** The child starts to question his place in the world. The child's identity, it is believed, comes from his parents. However, it is heartbreaking when a child's identity shadow is lifted. This leaves the child with a void in their life that nobody can fill.
- **Lack of Support for Education:** The majority of orphans find it challenging to educate themselves properly. It will be difficult for an orphan to get a college degree if they were too young when their parents died. Around the world, 10% of orphans end up having strong educational backgrounds. Even kids with two parents understand the difficulty and worry involved in getting them to school. It will require supernatural intervention if an orphan is to complete a proper educational program.
- **Less Probability of Success:** Compared to children that have parents, an orphan may have minimal odds of success. The main concerns of an orphan are always things like food, clothing, shelter, and survival. Housing or food may not be a child with parents' main concerns in life. They have parents who will give them almost everything they need in life.
- **Poor Communication Skills:** Orphans frequently choose to remain silent when they are reminded of their status. These kids might even experience isolation and rejection. Orphans who reside in their community may feel that their ideas are not necessary or needed. This makes it more challenging to build effective communication skills.

Psychological effects of bereavement

The loss of a parent while still a kid has been associated with a variety of grave and long-lasting health effects, including schizophrenia, significant depression, and suicide. The specific signs and syndromes of childhood grief are typically understood in terms of the immediate reactions that take place in the weeks and months after the tragedy, the intermediate reactions that can eventually appear in childhood

or adolescent years, and the long-term or " sleeper " effects that may manifest in adulthood as lingering effects or delayed reactions to the loss. The scientific evidence in this area is perhaps the poorest, even though these long-term impacts are the most concerning.

In the immediate aftermath of a parent's passing, children, like adults, exhibit a variety of emotional and behavioural responses. Children who have recently lost a parent or sibling are unhappy, angry, and scared, and they also exhibit behaviours such as withdrawal, difficulty concentrating, reliance, regression, fidgeting, and learning challenges. The age of the child who has lost a parent greatly affects the initial symptom patterns. Children under the age of two may exhibit loss of speech or generalized distress, while those under the age of five are likely to exhibit feeding, sleeping, bowel, and bladder abnormalities as a response. Children in the school-age range may develop phobias or hypochondriasis, become introverted, or become too nurturing. Especially in boys who struggle to communicate longing, aggressive outbursts may be seen in place of melancholy. Adolescents might react more maturely than adults, but they might also be hesitant to voice their feelings out of concern that they'll come out as odd or weird. People who lose a parent or sibling while they are young are thought to be most susceptible to developing depressive disorders later in life. Based on his clinical experience, Bowlby concluded that severe early loss makes people extremely susceptible to depressive disorders in the future, with each subsequent loss leading to an increase in unresolved grief that was originally connected to the early bereavement.

It is challenging to make judgments regarding the long-term effects of bereavement during childhood or adolescence. There are possible problems, but there isn't much information about what specifically puts a grieving youth in danger. In terms of intermediate effects, the data to date indicates that early mourning significantly raises a child's risk for depression, academic dysfunction, and criminality. Given the child's immaturity, it seems possible that even a brief depressive episode lasting 13 months might prevent or obstruct a child's typically developing ego, so obstructing or distorting psychological development. (Osterweis, Solomon, & Green, 1984)

Conclusion

The foster family is in the best position to care for the orphan child's additional medical, psychological, social, and educational needs because they have the knowledge and resources required to comprehend those needs as well as any potential psychological crises the child may be going through and how to handle them. Most of the responsibility lies with the state and the neighbourhood. The society in which the orphan child lives can play a major role in improving his circumstances. Many such children wind up living with family or other caregivers in low- and middle-income nations, where mental health treatment programs are typically unavailable. Trauma-focused cognitive behavioural therapy can be beneficial to such children. It is a form of talk therapy, that typically focuses on how changing ideas and behaviours can improve one's mood. Instead of attempting to tame thinking about or remembering the events, CBT for traumatic events encourages discussion about the incidents and any tough circumstances that may have arisen in the past.

Children can recover from traumatic events by making art and talking about it. Drawing, painting, modeling, collage, and other artistic activities are all possible. Activities like "Draw your safe place," "That's me," or free sketching can assist orphans and vulnerable kids in expressing their feelings, boosting their self-esteem, and processing unpleasant memories. Allowing kids to express themselves by drawing or painting whatever they choose and taking an interest in what they produce will suffice. To assist children and youth in addressing their sorrow and trauma, policymakers, schools, organisations, and the commercial sector can take appropriate action. The policies, initiatives, and practices to manage grieving and trauma that are supported by science should be explored.

In conclusion, research on childhood bereavement needs to adopt more contemporary norms. It is important to follow up with young individuals who have experienced the death of a parent to find out the short- and long-term effects of the loss and to pinpoint the subgroups most susceptible to pathological abnormalities. To find the most effective ways to assist children, intervention strategies must be put through efficacy studies. New or modified methods must be created in particular for pathologically grieving children.

References

1. Christodoulou, E., Asimakopoulou, E., Gourni, M., Argyriadi, A., Sapountzi-Krepia, D., Krepia, V., & Argiriadis, A. (2021). Depression Screening in Orphaned Children: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 14(2).
2. How orphanages harm children - Hope and Homes. Retrieved on 06 December 2022.
3. Kaur R., Vinnakota A., Panigrahi S. & Manasa R.V. (2018) A descriptive study on behavioural and emotional problems in orphans and other vulnerable children staying in institutional homes. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine* 40(2):161.
4. Lancet Article Sophisticated Trickery Intended To Create Panic Among Citizens, Divorced From Truth And Ground Reality: Ministry Of Women And Child Development. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=1802393>. Retrieved on 04 December 2022.
5. Mohammadzadeh M, Awang H, Kadir Shahar H & Ismail S. (2017) Emotional health and self-esteem among adolescents in Malaysian orphanages. *Community Mental Health Journal* 18:1-9.
6. Mudasir Naqshbandi, M., Sehgal, R., Abdullah, R., & Hassan, F. U. (2012). Orphans in orphanages of Kashmir" and their Psychological problems. *International NGO Journal*, 7(3).
7. Ntuli, B., Mokgatle, M., & Madiba, S. (2020). The psychosocial wellbeing of orphans: The case of early school leavers in socially depressed environment in Mpumalanga Province, South Africa. *PLoS ONE*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229487>
8. Orphan. (2022, November 29). In *Wikipedia*. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Orphan>
9. Orphan Outreach – Together we can restore hope – Country – India. Retrieved on 06 December 2022.
10. Osterweis, M., Solomon, F., & Green, M. (1984). Bereavement: Reactions, consequences, and care.
11. Priyadarshini D, Sandhiya & Rathnasabapathy, Maya. (2020). Behavioral And Emotional Problems Among Orphans: A Review Paper. 63. 14930-14936.
12. Research: Community-based Counselors Help Orphans with Trauma - DCID (duke.edu). Retrieved on 08 December 2022.
13. Sebsibe T., Fekadu D. & Molalign B. (2014) Psychosocial wellbeing of orphan and vulnerable children at orphanages in Gondar Town, North West Ethiopia. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology* 6(10):293-301.
14. Subih, Abdulrahman. (2020). What's an orphan child like's? (PDF) What's an orphan child like's? (researchgate.net)
15. Thakkar, A., Mepukori, D., Henschel, K., & Tran, T. (2020). Understanding attachment Patterns among Orphans in Residential Care Homes in New Delhi, India. *Institutionalised Children Explorations and Beyond*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2349301120150205>
16. the orphaned children, and the pain of bereavement - Violet Org (violetsyria.org). Retrieved on 06 December 2022.
17. The Pains That Orphan Children Pass Through In Life — Steemit. Retrieved on 06 December 2022.
18. Who Is An Orphan? – ONETrack International. Retrieved on 06 December 2022.